

Article

Methodological Openness and Social Sustainability in Secondary Education: Sociometric and Perceptual Evidence from Project-Based Learning

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Abstract

This study examines how methodological openness is associated with the social sustainability of learning in secondary education. A comparative, non-experimental, exploratory mixed-methods study was conducted with two secondary school classroom groups that completed the same technological task—the construction of a functional drawbridge—through two project-based learning configurations: a highly structured Guided Project and a more open STEM-PBL configuration. Data were collected through a sociometric questionnaire, a perceived group functioning scale, and open-ended student responses, yielding structural, perceptual, and qualitative evidence on classroom interaction. The results indicate that the open STEM-PBL configuration appeared to be associated with a more cohesive and integrated relational structure, reflected in higher reciprocity, lower isolation, and more distributed peer connections. Conversely, the more structured approach appeared to be associated with more positive and stable student perceptions of cooperative work, particularly in relation to responsibility, participation, peer support, and organizational stability. The central finding is a dissociation between the structural pattern of peer choices and students' perceived experience of cooperative group functioning. These exploratory findings suggest that socially sustainable learning environments depend not simply on expanding student autonomy, but on balancing openness, structure, and teacher mediation in ways that support relational inclusion, equitable participation, and group cohesion.

Keywords: social sustainability of learning; project-based learning; cooperative learning; sociometric analysis; secondary education; peer interaction; relational inclusion; group cohesion; STEM education

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1. Introduction

Group work is widely used in contemporary educational settings, particularly within active pedagogies. However, organizing students into teams does not, in itself, ensure effective cooperation or the development of complex social competencies. Research on cooperative learning has consistently shown that cooperation does not emerge automatically from group work; rather, it requires structured conditions such as positive interdependence, individual accountability, promotive interaction, and regulation of joint activity [1]. The distinction between merely working in groups and engaging in cooperative learning therefore remains central to understanding the quality of classroom interaction.

From a broader perspective, the social dimension of learning has become increasingly relevant in education, especially within approaches concerned with sustainability. In this

study, the social sustainability of learning is understood as the capacity of educational environments to sustain inclusive, equitable, and functional relationships among participants, while fostering group cohesion and the social competencies required for participation in complex societies [2–4]. It is operationalized through relational inclusion, equitable participation, group cohesion, and functionally meaningful cooperation across the learning process. Accordingly, the key issue is not simply whether students work in groups, but whether the instructional design supports relational integration, distributed participation, and shared regulation of learning activity.

Within this context, Project-Based Learning (PBL) has become one of the most prominent active pedagogies, as it engages students in authentic tasks, integrates knowledge across domains, and promotes transversal competencies [5,6]. Previous reviews have reported that PBL may contribute to academic learning and complex thinking skills, while also highlighting substantial heterogeneity in outcomes, largely related to differences in implementation [7–11]. One important factor underlying this variability is methodological openness, understood as the degree of student autonomy in problem definition, decision-making, and management of the work process. More open approaches may support joint knowledge construction and complex thinking, but they may also increase cognitive load and make group organization more demanding [12,13]. Conversely, more structured approaches may facilitate coordination and procedural stability, while potentially limiting opportunities for meaningful peer interaction. This tension between autonomy and structure is particularly relevant for understanding how different instructional configurations relate to the social dimension of learning.

Despite these advances, important gaps remain in the literature. Most studies on PBL have focused on academic achievement, motivation, or general perceptions of learning, while paying less attention to the relational structure of the group and its connection with students' lived experience [14,15]. Research on cooperative learning has also shown that the quality of peer interaction is a key predictor of learning [16,17], but many of these studies examine contexts in which cooperation is explicitly structured, which limits their transferability to more open methodological environments such as PBL. A further gap is that studies addressing the social dimension of learning frequently rely on self-report instruments alone, without incorporating direct relational measures capable of mapping peer interaction networks. Sociometry is particularly useful for examining patterns of cohesion, reciprocity, isolation, and segmentation within groups [18], although its use in recent research on active pedagogies in secondary education remains relatively limited. Integrating sociometric and perceptual evidence makes it possible to examine two complementary levels of analysis: the structural pattern of peer choices within the group and students' perceived experience of cooperative group functioning. As a result, empirical evidence remains limited on how different degrees of methodological openness simultaneously relate to peer relational structures, students' perceptions of cooperative work, and the social sustainability of learning.

Building on this background, the present study draws on cooperative learning, PBL, STEM education, and educational sustainability to analyze how different degrees of methodological openness are associated with the social dimension of learning in secondary education. Specifically, the study compares two project-based configurations: a highly structured Guided Project and a more open STEM-PBL configuration. Both were implemented through the same technological construction task: building a functional drawbridge in a secondary school technology classroom.

The contribution of this study is threefold. First, it incorporates sociometric analysis to examine the structural pattern of peer nominations, rather than relying solely on students' perceived experience of cooperative group functioning. Second, it compares two

project-based configurations that differ in their degree of pedagogical structuring, thereby contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the heterogeneity of PBL. Third, by integrating structural peer-nomination data, students' perceptions of cooperative work, and methodological openness as a configurational instructional variable, the study aims to offer exploratory empirical evidence of patterns of association that have remained underexplored in PBL research and in work on socially sustainable learning environments.

In particular, the study explores whether the structural pattern of peer choices and the perceived experience of cooperative work—two complementary levels of the social dimension of learning—co-vary across different methodological configurations, or whether they may diverge in informative ways. Based on this rationale, the study is guided by the following research question:

How are different degrees of methodological openness in project-based learning associated with peer relational structures and students' perceptions of cooperative group functioning in secondary education?

Building on the theoretical background developed in Section 2, the comparative logic of the study is articulated through three exploratory directional hypotheses. Given the non-experimental design, the absence of pretest measures, and the descriptive nature of the analyses (Section 6.2), these hypotheses are framed as prior exploratory expectations rather than as predictive hypotheses subjected to formal statistical testing. They are nevertheless made explicit in order to clarify the comparative logic of the study and to facilitate replication and falsification by future research using stronger designs.

Hypothesis 1 (structural pattern of peer choices). *It was expected that the more open STEM-PBL configuration—which broadens the space of within-group decisions and increases the demand for internal coordination—would be associated with a more distributed structural pattern of peer choices, reflected in higher reciprocity, fewer isolated students, and less marked segmentation, compared with the more structured Guided Project.*

Hypothesis 2 (perceived experience of cooperative work). *It was expected that the more structured Guided Project—which provides clearer task definitions, more predictable role distribution, and lower process uncertainty—would be associated with more positive and more homogeneous perceptions of cooperative group functioning, particularly in dimensions related to responsibility, organizational stability, and operational peer support.*

Hypothesis 3 (relationship between the two levels of evidence). *It was expected that the structural pattern of peer choices and the perceived experience of cooperative work would not necessarily co-vary across the two configurations. In particular, the configuration showing the more distributed structural pattern of peer choices was not expected to coincide with the configuration showing the more positive perceived group functioning. This third expectation is the central comparative proposition of the study.*

2. Background

2.1. Cooperative Learning and Social Interdependence

Cooperative learning has been one of the most influential frameworks in active pedagogies. From the early proposals of Johnson and Johnson [16,17], cooperative learning has been associated with the development of socio-affective competencies, mutual support, joint problem-solving, and shared responsibility for learning. The theory of social interdependence states that the way social interactions are structured—competitively, individually, or cooperatively—strongly influences participants' achievement and the relationships established among them.

Subsequent research has refined this framework, identifying conditions that make cooperative learning effective: positive interdependence, individual accountability, promotive interaction, social skills, and group processing [1]. From a sociocultural perspective, the quality of joint activity depends on how interaction is mediated [19–21]; without explicit structuring, group work tends to drift toward task division without meaningful interaction, with limited educational impact and frequent exclusion of less participatory students [16,17,22].

Recent research has also questioned the assumption that placing students in groups automatically produces cooperative learning. Studies on collaborative regulation indicate that collaboration does not automatically translate into productive interaction without explicit support [23]. Such evidence highlights the relevance of instructional design and teacher mediation in transforming group work into genuine cooperative learning [24].

2.2. Project-Based Learning and Methodological Variability

Project-Based Learning (PBL) is one of the most prominent active pedagogical approaches in contemporary education. It is characterized by engaging students in authentic, complex tasks that require integrating knowledge from different domains and producing concrete outputs [5,6]. PBL has been claimed to foster motivation, deep learning, transversal competencies, and authentic forms of student engagement [7].

Recent empirical work confirms, however, that PBL implementations are highly heterogeneous in their pedagogical design. A study of 46 STEAM-PBL instructional designs implemented across five Spanish secondary schools [25] documented substantial variability in how disciplinary integration, scaffolding, and student autonomy are operationalized, and identified persistent tensions between disciplinary depth and meta-disciplinary integration. This evidence supports a cautious reading of PBL outcomes and underlines the importance of describing the specific configuration of each implementation, rather than treating PBL as a single uniform pedagogical category.

At the same time, the literature is not uniformly optimistic. A recent systematic review of the impacts of open inquiry on students' learning in science [26] documents that open inquiry environments—including project-based and inquiry-based variants—pose substantial challenges related to high cognitive demand, the necessity of structured scaffolding, and the risks of inequity and disengagement when scaffolding is insufficient. This evidence provides a deliberate counterweight to optimistic readings of methodological openness and is engaged more fully in Section 5.

Despite these contributions, several limitations remain in the literature on PBL. Research has often focused on academic outcomes and individual motivation, while less attention has been paid to the structure of peer relationships [14,15] and to the conditions under which open methodologies sustain inclusive and equitable participation across all members of the group.

2.3. Methodological Openness and Pedagogical Configuration

Within PBL and other active pedagogies, methodological openness refers to the degree of student autonomy in problem definition, decision-making, organization of joint work, and management of the learning process. More open approaches transfer to students substantial responsibility for shaping the process, while more structured approaches define key elements of the task in advance.

Theoretical and empirical work suggests that openness can support deeper learning, complex thinking, and joint knowledge construction [13]. At the same time, increased openness raises the cognitive and organizational demands placed on students, and may amplify pre-existing inequalities when scaffolding is insufficient. Recent empirical work on

collaborative task design at the secondary education level [27] illustrates how relatively small variations in task structure shape the regulation of cooperative interaction, including how attention, planning, and monitoring are distributed across group members. This evidence supports a configurational reading of methodological openness, in which the design of the task and the form of teacher mediation jointly shape the social dynamics of cooperation.

From this perspective, methodological openness is not a neutral variable. Different configurations entail different patterns of teacher mediation, division of labour, regulation of interaction, and use of cognitive resources. For this reason, in the present study methodological openness is approached as a configurational variable—a methodological conglomerate that captures the joint variation of task definition, instructional scaffolding, student autonomy, and form of teacher mediation across the two pedagogical conditions compared in this study, rather than as a single independent variable that could be isolated from the rest of the configuration.

2.4. Social Sustainability of Learning: Conceptual Delimitation and Operationalization

The notion of the social sustainability of learning extends established frameworks on cooperative learning and educational sustainability. Within the broader sustainability agenda—and notably within Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education) and Sustainable Development Goal 10 (Reduced Inequalities) [2,28]—there is increasing recognition that the quality of learning environments depends not only on academic outcomes, but also on whether educational settings reproduce inclusive, equitable, and cohesive forms of participation across time and across participants.

The construct of the social sustainability of learning, as used in the present study, is not a synonym for cooperative learning. Whereas cooperative learning describes the conditions under which effective cooperation can emerge within a given learning episode—positive interdependence, individual accountability, promotive interaction, regulation, and interpersonal skills [1,16,17]—the social sustainability of learning refers to a property of the educational environment itself: its capacity to sustain inclusive ties, equitable participation, and functionally meaningful cooperation across participants over time. The two frameworks are therefore complementary rather than redundant. Whereas cooperative learning explains the conditions under which cooperation is structured within a learning episode, the social sustainability of learning refers to whether the relational conditions that make cooperation possible remain inclusive, distributed, and reproducible over time. A classroom environment may support effective cooperation within a single project while still failing to sustain inclusion and distributed participation across the broader relational network—the central observation that motivates the present comparative analysis.

In this study, the social sustainability of learning is operationalized through four observable properties of the classroom learning environment: (i) relational inclusion, operationalized through the absence of isolated students within the peer-nomination network; (ii) equitable participation, operationalized through the distribution of peer choices across the group and the absence of strong concentration on specific nodes; (iii) group cohesion, operationalized through the proportion of reciprocal positive nominations and the absence of marked segmentation; and (iv) functionally meaningful cooperation, operationalized through students' perceptions of cooperative group functioning and the qualitative analysis of their open-ended responses regarding peer support, responsibility, and interaction.

These four properties are observable at two complementary levels of evidence. The first three properties pertain to the structural pattern of peer choices within the group, which is examined through sociometric analysis. The fourth property pertains to students' perceived experience of cooperative group functioning, which is examined through the perceptual

questionnaire and the qualitative analysis. The combination of these two levels of evidence is methodologically informative because each level captures a distinct, but related, aspect of the social sustainability of learning, and their convergence or divergence carries direct interpretive value for understanding the relational quality of the learning environment.

The references to SDG 4 and SDG 10 are retained in this study as a broader normative context to which classroom-level findings may contribute, rather than as a direct evaluative framework for the present comparison. The broader sustainability implications of a small two-group classroom study are necessarily limited and are discussed accordingly in Sections 5 and 6.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Research Design

The study adopted a comparative, non-experimental, exploratory mixed-methods design. Quantitative data were obtained through a sociometric questionnaire and a perceived group functioning questionnaire, while qualitative data were collected through open-ended student responses. The integration of structural, perceptual, and qualitative data was intended to produce a multi-layered description of how methodological openness is associated with the social dimension of learning, rather than to test causal relationships among isolated variables. Given the absence of random assignment and of pretest measures, the comparison reported in this study should be understood as exploratory and descriptive, and the findings as patterns of association rather than as tested effects (see Section 6.2).

3.2. Participants and Context

The study was conducted with two intact lower secondary classroom groups from the same school, both enrolled in the same compulsory subject of Technology, at the same educational level, during the same academic year. The two groups were of comparable size, with a total of 67 students across both classes.

Several contextual indicators support the comparability of the two groups. First, both groups belonged to the same school, the same educational level, and the same subject; they worked in the same workshop-classroom environment and completed an equivalent technological task in terms of content, complexity, and learning objectives. Second, both groups shared the same school catchment area and admission profile, indicating an equivalent socioeconomic background. Third, available academic records indicated similar mean prior academic achievement across the two groups in the preceding term. Fourth, reports from the form tutor and the school orientation team—based on routine pedagogical follow-up at the start of the academic year—indicated comparable prior classroom dynamics and baseline social cohesion in the two groups. Fifth, both groups were taught by the same teacher under the same workshop-classroom conditions, with strictly equivalent instructional duration (eight weeks, two 55 min sessions per week, totaling approximately 14 h and 40 min per group).

Notwithstanding these convergent contextual indicators, no formal pretest measure of academic achievement, group cohesion, or sociometric structure was administered prior to the intervention. The equivalence claims therefore rest on contextual indicators rather than on direct baseline measurements. This limitation is acknowledged in Section 6.2, alongside other uncontrolled classroom-level variables that may have contributed to the observed differences between the two configurations.

3.3. Pedagogical Conditions

Both groups completed the same technological construction task: the design, construction, and presentation of a functional drawbridge in the school workshop/classroom. The

task involved a complete production cycle (problem analysis, design, construction, testing, communication) and required the integration of basic knowledge in mechanics, materials, electricity, and teamwork. The two groups completed the same task under two distinct pedagogical configurations.

3.3.1. Group 1: Guided Project

The first group followed a Guided Project (GP) configuration, in which the teacher provided detailed instructions about every stage of the process: clearly defined work phases, predetermined functional requirements for the artifact, explicit role assignments within each work team, predefined sequence of tasks, and direct intermediate supervision. The teacher's mediation in this condition was predominantly directive, focused on the correct execution of the predetermined sequence and on the achievement of the standardized output. Methodological openness in this configuration was therefore deliberately low.

3.3.2. Group 2: Open Functional STEM Project-Based Approach

The second group followed an open functional STEM project-based approach (hereafter, open STEM-PBL configuration), in which students were given a problem space defined by the same final goal (a functional drawbridge) but were responsible for substantial autonomous decisions: definition of the specific design, internal organization of the group, distribution of roles and sub-tasks, planning of the work process, management of materials and time, and selection of construction strategies. The teacher's mediation in this condition was predominantly process-regulatory, focused on scaffolding student decisions, mediating conflicts, and supporting the regulation of joint activity, while leaving substantive decisions to the students.

3.3.3. General Comparison of the Pedagogical Conditions

Both pedagogical configurations were implemented by the same teacher under the same workshop-classroom conditions. The use of a single teacher across the two conditions substantially reduces concerns related to between-teacher variability, which is a common source of confounding in comparative classroom research. At the same time, it must be acknowledged that teacher mediation could not be held entirely constant across the two conditions, because the two pedagogical configurations themselves call for structurally different forms of mediation (directive guidance in the Guided Project; process regulation, scaffolding, and conflict mediation in the open STEM-PBL configuration). This difference in teacher mediation is therefore not a flaw of the implementation but a constitutive feature of the methodological contrast itself. The comparison between conditions should accordingly be understood as a contrast between two pedagogical configurations as wholes—each combining a specific degree of methodological openness with its associated form of teacher mediation—rather than as a comparison of methodological openness in isolation. This implication for the interpretation of the findings is discussed further in Section 6.2.

Table 1 summarizes the main features of the two pedagogical configurations. The comparison is intended to clarify that the contrast examined in this study does not isolate methodological openness as a single variable, but rather compares two instructional configurations that differ simultaneously in task definition, student autonomy, work sequence, teacher mediation, expected forms of cooperation, treatment of errors, and level of uncertainty.

Table 1. Main features of the two pedagogical configurations.

Dimension	Guided Project	Open Functional STEM Project-Based Approach
Task definition	Defined by the teacher	Defined as an open problem space
Technical solution	Predetermined model	Developed by each team
Student autonomy	Low; focused on execution and organization	High; focused on design, planning, and decision-making
Work sequence	Predefined and linear	Open, iterative, and adjustable
Teacher mediation	Directive guidance and supervision	Process regulation, scaffolding, and conflict mediation
Type of cooperation expected	Operational coordination	Deliberative coordination and shared regulation
Treatment of errors	Correction of deviations from the model	Testing, adjustment, and redesign
Level of uncertainty	Low	High

Note. The table summarizes the methodological contrast as a comparison between two pedagogical configurations as wholes, rather than as an isolated manipulation of methodological openness.

3.4. Instruments

3.4.1. Sociometric Questionnaire

A sociometric questionnaire was administered to each group at the end of the intervention. Sociometric methodology, originally developed within the social psychology tradition [29], has been increasingly applied in educational research to map the relational structure of classroom groups and to identify patterns of inclusion, cohesion, and isolation. Recent applications of sociometric and social network analysis to peer interaction networks in secondary education [30,31] have documented its value for examining inclusion, sense of belonging, and contingent network effects in school settings. The present study adopts a descriptive sociometric approach within this tradition, while restricting the analysis to descriptive structural indicators (see Sections 3.5 and 6.2).

The questionnaire was administered individually and confidentially. It included three types of sociometric prompts: positive nominations, negative nominations, and sociometric-perception nominations. These prompts were administered at two levels of analysis: the work-group level and the whole-class level. Positive nominations captured students' preferred peers for collaboration; negative nominations captured peers with whom collaboration was perceived as difficult or less desirable; and sociometric-perception prompts captured students' expectations about who would choose them. The number of nominations per item was limited to two or three classmates. The present analysis focused primarily on positive and negative nominations, from which reciprocity, isolation, rejection patterns, and tie distribution were derived. The wording of the items was age-appropriate and the survey was conducted with prior informed consent from legal guardians (see Section 3.6).

3.4.2. Perceived Group Functioning Questionnaire

A complementary questionnaire was administered to capture students' perceptions of cooperative group functioning during the project. The instrument addressed perceptions of responsibility, peer support, participation, communication, conflict management, and organizational stability within the group, building on dimensions widely recognized in

the cooperative learning and group-interaction literature [1,16,17,32]. Items used a 5-point Likert response format.

Regarding methodological quality, the instrument is grounded in dimensions widely recognized in the literature on cooperative learning and peer interaction, which supports its content validity. The comparative analysis was conducted on the basis of group-level aggregated scores and item- and dimension-level means. Individual-level item responses were not retained after data aggregation, and therefore no estimate of internal consistency (e.g., Cronbach's α , McDonald's ω) could be computed retrospectively. The questionnaire findings should consequently be interpreted as descriptive indicators of perceived group functioning, not as psychometrically validated measures of latent constructs. This methodological constraint is reflected in cautious wording throughout Sections 4–6, and is acknowledged in Section 6.2.

3.4.3. Open-Ended Items

At the end of the perceived group functioning questionnaire, students responded to a set of open-ended items inviting them to describe what they had valued most in the cooperative work, what difficulties they had encountered, and how they perceived peer support and organization within the group. The corpus generated by these responses was used as a qualitative complement to the quantitative analysis (see Section 3.5).

3.5. Data Analysis

The sociometric component was analyzed descriptively from the nomination matrices. Each reported indicator was computed as follows. Reciprocity was operationalized as the proportion of mutual positive nominations relative to the total number of positive nominations issued at each level of analysis (work-group and whole-class). Isolation was operationalized as the proportion of students who did not receive any positive nomination at each level of analysis. Rejection patterns were derived from the negative-nomination matrix and inspected for concentrations on specific individuals or evidence of group segmentation. Tie distribution was assessed by visually examining the resulting sociograms and the dispersion of nominations across the network.

The analysis is therefore limited to descriptive sociometric indicators; formal Social Network Analysis (SNA) metrics—such as density, clustering coefficient, or degree and betweenness centrality—were not computed because the original individual-level binary nomination matrices were not preserved at the individual level after data aggregation. The corresponding methodological constraint is acknowledged in Section 6.2.

The qualitative component was analyzed through an inductive thematic approach. The qualitative corpus consisted of approximately 150–200 open-ended responses, distributed similarly across the two pedagogical conditions. The coding procedure was carried out by two members of the research team, who independently read the full corpus, identified meaning units, and grouped them into emerging categories related to the analytical dimensions of the study. Discrepancies between the two coders were discussed until consensus was reached, with the broader research team consulted in cases of persistent disagreement. Main categories emerged inductively from repeated readings of the responses; a formal structured codebook with operational definitions was not produced, although the main emerging categories can be made available upon reasonable request. Representative quotations were selected to illustrate the most frequent and characteristic formulations within each category, while preserving anonymity. A formal inter-rater agreement coefficient (e.g., Cohen's κ) was not computed, given the exploratory and complementary nature of the qualitative component within the broader mixed-methods design; this choice is acknowledged as a methodological limitation in Section 6.2.

Given that individual-level item responses were not preserved and only aggregated group-level scores were available, inferential statistical testing (e.g., non-parametric tests, effect-size estimators, confidence intervals) could not be conducted. The quantitative component of the study is therefore strictly descriptive and exploratory, and the comparisons reported between the two pedagogical conditions should be interpreted as patterns of association observed in the available data, rather than as statistically tested differences. This constraint is reflected in cautious wording throughout the Results, Discussion, and Conclusions, and is acknowledged as a substantive limitation in Section 6.2.

3.6. Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in full compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Spanish Organic Law 3/2018 on the Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights (LOPDGDD). It was carried out as part of regular classroom activity, with the prior agreement of the school's management team. Given that the sociometric instrument included both positive and negative nominations among adolescent peers, a comprehensive set of safeguards was adopted to prevent psychosocial risks and to protect participants throughout the procedure. These safeguards are described below.

Written informed consent was obtained from the students' legal guardians prior to the administration of the instruments. Student assent was obtained before participation. The activity was conducted with the prior agreement of the school's management team, as part of regular classroom activity, in compliance with applicable data protection regulations.

Anonymity was strictly preserved at the classroom level: individual responses were never returned to the class, displayed publicly, or discussed in students' presence. Identities were coded prior to analysis, so that individual nominations were never associated with student names in any analytical or reporting stage. No individual or group-level sociometric results were ever shared, displayed, or discussed in the classroom.

The questionnaire was administered individually and confidentially, with students answering without seeing the responses of their peers and without group discussion of the items. The administration was supervised by the regular classroom teacher, who was available to detect and address any sign of discomfort during the procedure.

Prior to administration, the pedagogical and research purpose of the questionnaire was explicitly explained, clarifying that it was not part of any personal or group academic evaluation. Participation was explicitly voluntary, and students were informed that they could decline to respond to any item or withdraw at any moment without consequence.

The number of nominations—both positive and negative—was limited to between two and three per item, in line with established sociometric practice [33,34].

The procedure was conducted with the prior agreement of the school's management team and integrated into routine pedagogical activity. As a residual limitation, no formal post-administration debriefing session was conducted; this is acknowledged in Section 6.2 as a minor methodological limitation that future replications should address.

4. Results

The results are presented sequentially. First, the overall profile of cooperative work is described at the dimension level (Section 4.1). Second, the structural pattern of peer choices is analyzed through sociometric indicators (Section 4.2). Third, micro-level results regarding responsibility, interdependence, and forms of participation are reported (Section 4.3), followed by the analysis of internal variability across teams (Section 4.4). Fourth, the nature of cooperation across the two configurations is examined through the integrated analysis of quantitative and qualitative evidence (Section 4.5), and the patterns related to peer support, teacher mediation, and conflict are presented (Section 4.6). Fifth, an integrated

figure synthesizes the two complementary levels of evidence (Section 4.7). Finally, partial findings on individual variables are reported (Section 4.8). For each block, the analysis is descriptive, and the comparisons between the two pedagogical configurations should be interpreted as patterns of association observed in the available data.

4.1. Overall Profile of Cooperative Work by Methodological Approach

Analysis of the perceived group functioning questionnaire revealed differentiated profiles across the two methodological approaches. Overall, both the Guided Project and the open STEM-PBL configuration obtained relatively high scores in dimensions related to responsibility and knowledge exchange. This pattern is consistent with the idea that, regardless of the methodological approach, group work supported task fulfillment and the circulation of cognitive peer support. The most pronounced descriptive differences between conditions, however, appeared in profile homogeneity, rating stability across dimensions, and the internal variability associated with each methodological approach. Table 2 presents the comparative profile of cooperative work dimensions by methodology.

Table 2. Comparative profile of cooperative work dimensions by methodological approach.

Dimension	Guided Project Mean (%)	Range	SD ^a	Open Functional STEM Project-Based Approach Mean (%)	Range	SD ^a	Interpretation
Individual and group responsibility	4.23 (84.7%)	3.80–4.65	0.31	3.77 (75.3%)	3.00–4.60	0.57	Higher and more stable in the Guided Project
Communication skills	3.78 (75.7%)	3.05–4.15	0.38	3.79 (75.8%)	3.05–4.20	0.44	Essentially equivalent values
Knowledge exchange	4.23 (84.7%)	3.93–4.60	0.25	3.81 (76.2%)	3.40–4.27	0.33	Higher and more homogeneous in the Guided Project
Participation	3.78 (75.5%)	3.40–4.35	0.41	3.23 (64.7%)	2.65–3.80	0.40	Higher in the Guided Project
Competence achievement	4.15 (83.1%)	3.88–4.44	0.24	3.74 (74.8%)	3.36–4.28	0.35	Higher in the Guided Project
Conflict occurrence ^b	1.97 (39.3%)	1.40–2.60	0.45	2.23 (44.7%)	1.80–3.20	0.56	Greater perceived conflict occurrence in the open STEM-PBL configuration
Willingness to resolve conflicts	3.90 (78.0%)	3.20–4.80	0.60	3.90 (78.0%)	2.60–4.80	0.86	Similar willingness, with greater variability in the open STEM-PBL configuration

^a SD = standard deviation. ^b In the “conflict occurrence” dimension, lower scores indicate a more favorable rating because they reflect lower perceived frequency of conflict.

As shown in Table 2, the Guided Project obtained higher mean scores in most dimensions, particularly responsibility, knowledge exchange, participation, and competence achievement. These dimensions also showed lower dispersion, showing patterns consistent

with a more stable and homogeneous perceived profile of cooperative functioning across teams. By contrast, the open STEM-PBL configuration showed greater variability, especially in responsibility and in indicators related to conflict occurrence and conflict resolution. On the communication skills dimension, the two configurations showed essentially equivalent values (75.7% vs. 75.8%), and no interpretive emphasis is attached to this near-identical contrast. Overall, the more structured methodology appeared to be associated with a more homogeneous perceived profile of cooperative functioning, whereas the open STEM-PBL configuration showed greater internal variability across teams.

4.2. Relational Structure and Sociometric Analysis of the Interaction Network

The sociometric analysis showed that the descriptive differences between the two methodological approaches were not limited to students' perceptions but also appeared in the structural pattern of peer choices within the group. Overall, the group that worked through the open STEM-PBL configuration showed a more cohesive, distributed, and interconnected relational network than the Guided Project group. Table 3 presents the comparative sociometric indicators.

Table 3. Comparative sociometric indicators.

Indicator	Guided Project	Open Functional STEM Project-Based Approach
Reciprocity at work-group level	21.2%	30.0%
Reciprocity at whole-class level	33.3%	43.3%
Isolated students at work-group level	9.1%	0.0%
Isolated students at whole-class level	9.1%	3.3%
Gender-based segregation	Present	Not evident

Note. Percentages were calculated relative to the total number of students in each group. For reciprocity, the percentage should be interpreted as a descriptive index relative to group size, since the unit of analysis is reciprocal ties rather than individual students. Indicators are descriptive structural measures computed from the nomination matrices; no formal Social Network Analysis metrics or inferential tests are reported (see Sections 3.5 and 6.2).

As Table 3 shows, the open STEM-PBL configuration showed descriptively higher reciprocity than the Guided Project both at the work-group level (30.0% vs. 21.2%) and at the whole-class level (43.3% vs. 33.3%), as well as a lower proportion of isolated students (0.0% vs. 9.1% at the work-group level; 3.3% vs. 9.1% at the whole-class level). Patterns of gender-based segregation were also less evident in the open STEM-PBL group than in the Guided Project group. These descriptive differences should be interpreted in light of the exploratory and non-inferential nature of the analysis (Section 6.2).

Beyond aggregate counts, the distribution of choices differed across the two configurations. In the Guided Project, choices and rejections tended to concentrate around specific nodes, showing a pattern consistent with a more hierarchical and segmented relational structure. In the open STEM-PBL configuration, relationships were more evenly distributed across members, showing a pattern consistent with a more open and interconnected network. The structural analysis is therefore consistent with the idea that the open STEM-PBL configuration appeared to be associated with a more distributed structural pattern of peer choices than the Guided Project.

4.3. Micro-Level Results: Responsibility, Interdependence, and Forms of Participation

Item-level analysis revealed patterns that were not fully visible in the aggregated dimension scores. In the responsibility dimension, the highest scores were concentrated in items related to fulfilling one's own tasks and meeting deadlines, whereas lower scores appeared in items related to knowing classmates' tasks. Table 4 presents the key responsibility and interdependence items by methodological approach.

Table 4. Key responsibility and interdependence items by methodological approach.

Item	Guided Project	Open Functional STEM Project-Based Approach	Interpretation
I worked as I had committed to at the beginning (1.1)	4.10 (82.0%)	3.50 (70.0%)	Greater individual responsibility in the Guided Project
Deadlines were met (1.2)	4.57 (91.3%)	3.37 (67.3%)	Clear difference in favor of the Guided Project
I knew the tasks I had to perform (1.3)	4.37 (87.3%)	3.83 (76.7%)	High individual responsibility in both groups
I knew the tasks my classmates had to perform (1.4)	3.90 (78.0%)	3.63 (72.7%)	Interdependence weaker than individual responsibility

Note. Percentages were calculated relative to the maximum value of the five-point Likert scale.

As Table 4 shows, descriptive differences between the two approaches were particularly clear in the items related to fulfilling commitments and meeting deadlines. Students in the Guided Project obtained higher scores in all responsibility items, especially deadline fulfillment. However, in both methodological conditions, students' knowledge of their classmates' tasks scored lower than items associated with individual responsibility. This pattern is consistent with the idea that individual responsibility was more consolidated than structured interdependence: students showed a relatively solid orientation toward fulfilling their own tasks, but a weaker awareness of the team's overall functioning.

The qualitative responses supported this interpretation. In the Guided Project, students' comments more often referred to the functional division of work, as in "we divided the group. . . some cut and others took measurements." In the open STEM-PBL configuration, responses such as "everyone contributes different ideas" or "I could not do it by myself" showed patterns consistent with a more cognitive than operational form of interdependence.

A second relevant micro-level pattern was the dissociation between participation and knowledge exchange. In both groups, knowledge exchange obtained higher scores than participation, showing patterns consistent with cognitive peer support that was not necessarily accompanied by balanced involvement from all group members. The nature of participation also differed between the two conditions. In the Guided Project, participation was mainly oriented toward task execution and operational coordination. In the open STEM-PBL configuration, participation was more closely related to discussion, decision-making, and the contribution of ideas, although with greater inequality among members. These patterns support a tentative interpretive distinction between operational participation, more closely associated with the Guided Project, and deliberative participation, more closely associated with the open STEM-PBL configuration. Table 5 summarizes this distinction.

Table 5. Types of participation by methodological approach.

Type of Participation	Guided Project	Open Functional STEM Project-Based Approach	Interpretation
Operational participation	3.9 (78.0%)	3.3 (66.0%)	More closely associated with the Guided Project
Deliberative participation	3.4 (68.0%)	3.8 (76.0%)	More closely associated with the open STEM-PBL configuration

Note. Operational participation refers to task execution and coordination; deliberative participation refers to discussion, decision-making, and contribution of ideas. The distinction is presented here as a tentative interpretive typology derived from the integrated analysis of questionnaire items and open-ended responses, rather than as an empirically measured construct (see Section 6.2).

4.4. Internal Variability Across Teams

In addition to descriptive differences between methodological approaches, internal variability across teams emerged as an important pattern, particularly in the open STEM-PBL configuration. Although this condition showed a more positive overall sociometric profile, the disaggregated team-level analysis revealed considerable heterogeneity in responsibility, participation, conflict, and perceptions of shared work.

In the open STEM-PBL group, some teams obtained low responsibility scores, approximately between 2.8 and 3.0 on the five-point scale. These teams also showed lower contribution of ideas, stronger perceptions of unequal participation, and greater difficulties in conflict management. In addition, concentrations of rejection toward specific members appeared in some teams, showing patterns consistent with the idea that greater methodological openness did not produce homogeneous patterns across all groups.

These differences were also reflected in students' open-ended responses, with comments such as "some people work more than others" or "some people do not let others work." These responses showed patterns consistent with a clear perception of unequal involvement and difficulties in sustaining balanced cooperative dynamics. Overall, the open STEM-PBL configuration showed greater internal heterogeneity across teams than the Guided Project.

4.5. Nature of Cooperation: Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Data

The qualitative analysis of open-ended responses provided further insight into the nature of cooperation in the two conditions. In Group 1, which worked through the Guided Project, students' responses tended to emphasize efficiency, task distribution, and practical peer support. These comments showed patterns consistent with instrumental cooperation, linked to finishing earlier, progressing faster, or distributing work in a functional way.

By contrast, in Group 2, which worked through the open STEM-PBL configuration, responses more often referred to idea exchange, diversity of perspectives, shared discussion, and the impossibility of completing the project individually. These comments showed patterns consistent with a more cognitive form of cooperation, based on deliberation, joint reflection, and shared knowledge construction. Table 6 summarizes this tentative interpretive distinction.

Table 6. Nature of cooperation by methodological approach.

Type of Cooperation	Predominant Features	Associated Methodological Approach
Operational cooperation	Task division, efficiency, practical support, execution	Guided Project
Cognitive-deliberative cooperation	Discussion, idea exchange, reflection, co-construction	Open functional STEM project-based approach

Note. This typology was developed inductively from the qualitative analysis of students' open-ended responses. It is presented as a tentative interpretive typology rather than as an empirically measured construct; no observational or discourse-analytic data were collected to substantiate claims regarding the cognitive complexity of peer interaction (see Section 6.2).

These descriptive patterns suggest that the two configurations differed not only in the amount of student interaction but also in its qualitative character: the Guided Project appeared more closely linked to stable, functional cooperation oriented toward task completion, whereas the open STEM-PBL configuration appeared more closely linked to deliberative forms based on discussion and shared meaning-making, as inferred from the qualitative analysis.

4.6. Peer Support, Teacher Mediation, and Conflict

One notable descriptive finding concerns how groups managed support and conflict during the work process. Group 1, which worked through the Guided Project, showed a greater tendency to resolve difficulties through peer support. Group 2, which worked through the open STEM-PBL configuration, showed a higher recourse to the teacher. Table 7 presents the comparative scores for peer support, recourse to the teacher, and conflict resolution.

Table 7. Comparative scores for peer support, teacher mediation, and conflict resolution.

Aspect	Guided Project	Open Functional STEM Project-Based Approach	Interpretation
Peer support	4.0 (80.0%)	3.4 (68.0%)	Greater operational self-sufficiency in the Guided Project
Recourse to the teacher	3.2 (64.0%)	4.2 (84.0%)	Greater reliance on teacher mediation in the open STEM-PBL configuration
Conflict resolution	3.4 (68.0%)	3.0 (60.0%)	Greater complexity in the open STEM-PBL configuration

Note. Percentages were calculated relative to the maximum value of the five-point Likert scale.

As shown in Table 7, the management of support and conflict followed differentiated patterns across the two approaches. Although the open STEM-PBL configuration offered more opportunities for decision-making, it also increased the complexity of the process and, with it, the descriptive need for teacher mediation. Both groups regarded the teacher as a relevant agent in resolving difficulties. Regarding conflict, the open STEM-PBL group showed a descriptively higher frequency of disagreements and greater variability in their resolution. However, both groups showed a similar declared willingness to resolve conflicts.

4.7. Integrated Figure of Results

Figure 1 provides a synthetic visual representation of the central observation arising from the integrated analysis. The upper panel presents the comparative profile of the dimensions of perceived group functioning across the two configurations, showing a more homogeneous pattern in the Guided Project and greater variability in the open STEM-PBL configuration. The lower panel summarizes the main sociometric indicators, showing a more distributed structural pattern of peer choices in the open STEM-PBL configuration and a more segmented pattern in the Guided Project.

Considered together, both panels illustrate the central observation of the study: the dissociation between the structural pattern of peer choices and the perceived experience of cooperative group functioning. The configuration showing the more distributed structural pattern of peer choices (open STEM-PBL) did not coincide with the configuration showing the more positive perceived group functioning (Guided Project).

4.8. Individual Variables

The analysis of individual variables did not reveal conclusive gender-based differences across the dimensions assessed. Mean scores for responsibility, communication, participation, and knowledge exchange did not show consistent patterns between boys and girls in either group. However, some partial indications were identified. In the Guided Project group, boys tended to report a higher presence of conflict in group work than girls, whereas in the open STEM-PBL group this pattern did not appear clearly.

At the sociometric level, some localized patterns of gender-based grouping and descriptively higher reciprocity among girls appeared in certain classroom dynamics. However,

because groups were formed spontaneously by students and the observed patterns were not consistent across contexts, gender cannot be considered a primary explanatory variable for cooperative group functioning in this study.

Figure 1. Integrated profile of results by methodological approach. Upper panel: comparative radar chart of the dimensions of perceived group functioning. Lower panel: bar chart of the main sociometric indicators. Together, the figure illustrates a dissociation between the structural pattern of peer choices—more distributed in the open STEM-PBL configuration—and the perceived experience of cooperative group functioning—more positive in the Guided Project.

5. Discussion

The aim of this study was to examine how different degrees of methodological openness in project-based learning are associated with peer relational structures and students' perceptions of cooperative group functioning in secondary education. Three exploratory directional hypotheses guided the comparative logic of the study (Section 1).

Regarding Hypothesis 1, the comparison of the structural pattern of peer choices across the two configurations was consistent with the exploratory expectation. The open STEM-PBL configuration showed descriptively higher reciprocity of positive nominations, lower isolation, and a more distributed pattern of peer choices than the Guided Project, both

at the work-group and at the whole-class levels of analysis. These patterns are consistent with the idea that broader within-group decision-making and a higher demand for internal coordination may favour a more distributed relational structure, although the descriptive nature of the analysis precludes any causal claim.

Regarding Hypothesis 2, the comparison of the perceived experience of cooperative work was also consistent with the exploratory expectation. The Guided Project configuration showed descriptively higher mean scores across most dimensions of perceived group functioning, particularly in dimensions related to responsibility, organizational stability, peer support, and participation. These patterns are consistent with the idea that clearer task definitions, more predictable role distribution, and lower process uncertainty may favour more positive and more homogeneous perceptions of cooperative group functioning.

Regarding Hypothesis 3, which constituted the central comparative proposition of the study, the two levels of evidence did not align. The configuration showing the more distributed structural pattern of peer choices (open STEM-PBL) was not the configuration showing the more positive perceived group functioning (Guided Project). This dissociation between the structural pattern of peer choices and the perceived experience of cooperative work is the central interpretive observation of the present study.

From the perspective of cooperative learning theory [1,16,17], this dissociation can be read as reflecting two distinct aspects of cooperation. The more structured Guided Project configuration appears to support what the qualitative analysis described as operational cooperation: clearly defined roles, predictable mutual help, and stable coordination around predetermined tasks. The more open STEM-PBL configuration appears to support more deliberative forms of cooperation: discussion of design choices, negotiation of disagreements, joint decision-making, and shared regulation of the process. Although the present study did not directly measure cognitive engagement, this interpretation is compatible with frameworks that distinguish different modes of student engagement and highlight the relevance of constructive and interactive participation [35]. The latter forms of interaction are inferred from the qualitative analysis and are not based on observational or discourse-analytic data; further empirical work using such methodologies would be necessary to substantiate claims regarding the cognitive complexity of peer interaction.

At the same time, the present findings should be situated within broader and more critical debates on cooperative learning and PBL. Research on open inquiry environments documents that, when scaffolding and structured interdependence are insufficient, openness may increase cognitive overload, inequity, and social exclusion [12,13,26]. Studies on collaborative regulation indicate that the presence of group work does not automatically translate into productive interaction; explicit support for the regulation of joint activity is needed for cooperation to translate into learning [23,27]. Recent work on PBL implementations further documents substantial heterogeneity in design choices and persistent tensions between disciplinary depth and meta-disciplinary integration [25]. The interpretation of the present findings should therefore acknowledge that openness, by itself, is not a guarantee of socially sustainable learning; rather, its educational effects depend on the form of teacher mediation and the structure of interdependence that accompany it.

Two further interpretive observations follow from the analysis. First, the two pedagogical configurations appear to support distinct dimensions of cooperation rather than to constitute alternatives of unequal value. Second, the central interpretive proposition of the study—that socially sustainable learning environments may require a deliberate balance among autonomy, structure, and teacher mediation—is presented as an interpretive contribution open to further inquiry, rather than as a definitive empirical claim.

Methodologically, the present study illustrates the value of combining sociometric and perceptual evidence in research on the social dimension of learning. Each level of evidence

captures a distinct, but related, aspect of the classroom learning environment, and their convergence or divergence carries direct interpretive value. The dissociation reported here would have remained invisible if only one of the two levels of evidence had been analyzed.

Taken together, the present findings suggest that methodological openness is associated with the social dimension of learning in complex and partly counterintuitive ways. More open methodological configurations may support more distributed relational structures, but they may also entail organizational and relational demands that affect students' perceived experience of cooperative work, particularly when explicit scaffolding for the regulation of joint activity is limited. Conversely, more structured configurations may support more positive perceptions of cooperative functioning but may also produce more segmented relational structures across the wider classroom network. The interpretation of these patterns developed in this section motivates the broader conclusions presented in Section 6.

6. Conclusions

This study has examined, through an exploratory comparative mixed-methods design, how two project-based learning configurations differing in their degree of methodological openness—a Guided Project and an open functional STEM project-based approach—are associated with the social dimension of learning in secondary education. Three exploratory conclusions follow from the integrated analysis.

First, the more open STEM-PBL configuration was descriptively associated with a more distributed structural pattern of peer choices, reflected in higher reciprocity, lower isolation, and a more cohesive whole-class structure. Second, the more structured Guided Project configuration was descriptively associated with more positive and more homogeneous perceptions of cooperative group functioning, particularly in dimensions related to responsibility, organizational stability, peer support, and participation. Third, the two levels of evidence did not align: the configuration showing the more distributed structural pattern of peer choices was not the configuration showing the more positive perceived group functioning. This dissociation is presented as the central observation arising from the comparison, suitable as an empirical basis for further research rather than as conclusive evidence regarding socially sustainable learning environments.

From an educational point of view, these findings suggest that methodological openness is associated with the social dimension of learning in complex ways. Openness alone is not sufficient to ensure socially sustainable learning environments; nor is structure alone sufficient to ensure equitable participation across the wider relational network. The interpretive proposition that follows from the analysis—and that is open to further inquiry—is that socially sustainable learning environments may require a deliberate balance among autonomy, structure, and teacher mediation, supporting at once relational inclusion, equitable participation, group cohesion, and substantive cooperative interaction.

6.1. Educational Implications

The educational implications that follow from this study are formulated as tentative suggestions for practice pending replication, rather than as generalizable prescriptions. They are grounded in the exploratory patterns described above and should be tested in further research using stronger designs. Five clusters of suggestions are proposed.

- (i) Structuring interdependence explicitly. Open methodological configurations may benefit from explicit structuring of positive interdependence—for example, through shared goals, complementary roles, and group-level accountability mechanisms—so that the wider opportunity for distributed participation translates into substantive cooperative interaction rather than into informal task division.

- (ii) Distinguishing operational from deliberative participation. The interpretive distinction between operational and deliberative cooperation suggests that instructional designs benefit from supporting both forms simultaneously: operational support for stable coordination, and deliberative support for joint decision-making, negotiation of disagreements, and shared regulation of the process.
- (iii) Monitoring relational inclusion alongside task progress. The dissociation reported in this study suggests that monitoring task progress is not sufficient on its own. Brief, periodic, anonymous sociometric snapshots of the classroom—used pedagogically and never publicly displayed—could help teachers identify peripheral or isolated students before relational difficulties consolidate, in parallel with the regular follow-up of task progress.
- (iv) Forms of teacher mediation in open STEM-PBL contexts. Open STEM-PBL configurations call for forms of teacher mediation that differ from content delivery. Five forms appear particularly relevant: (a) process-regulation mediations focused on planning, monitoring, and reflective review of joint activity, rather than on content delivery; (b) scaffolded conflict-management protocols that support students in negotiating disagreements within the work-group; (c) brief guided debrief moments at the end of work sessions, focused on what the group decided and how decisions were taken; (d) predictable scaffolding milestones across the project, balancing openness with sufficient organizational support; and (e) relational mediation, with active support for the integration of peripheral students into group dynamics. These forms of mediation are not specific to STEM-PBL but appear particularly relevant when methodological openness increases the demand for internal coordination.
- (v) Balancing openness with structure. The patterns reported here are consistent with the idea that the educational value of methodological openness depends on the form of structure and teacher mediation that accompany it. A deliberate balance between openness, structure, and teacher mediation—calibrated to the age of students, the nature of the task, and the prior dynamics of the group—appears more promising than the adoption of openness or structure as default pedagogical orientations.

Each of these clusters is offered as a conjectural educational implication, derived from the exploratory patterns described in this two-group study and open to revision in light of further empirical work.

6.2. Limitations and Future Research

The interpretation of the present findings is subject to a set of methodological limitations that should be made fully explicit.

- (1) Sample, design, and configurational nature of the comparison. The study compares two intact classroom groups ($n = 67$ total) from a single secondary school, without random assignment to conditions and without formal pretest measures of academic achievement, group cohesion, or sociometric structure. The equivalence claims regarding the two groups rest on contextual indicators rather than on direct baseline measurements (Section 3.2). In addition, although both pedagogical configurations were implemented by the same teacher—which substantially reduces concerns related to between-teacher variability—teacher mediation could not be held entirely constant across the two conditions, because the two configurations themselves call for structurally different forms of mediation. The comparison reported here should accordingly be understood as a contrast between two pedagogical configurations as wholes—each combining a specific degree of methodological openness with its associated form of teacher mediation—rather than as a comparison of methodological openness in isolation. Other uncontrolled classroom-level variables (e.g., subtle

differences in prior group dynamics, student composition effects) may also have contributed to the observed differences.

- (2) Psychometric basis of the perceptual instrument. The perceived group functioning questionnaire is grounded in dimensions widely recognized in the cooperative learning literature, which supports its content validity. However, because individual-level item responses were not preserved after data aggregation, no estimate of internal consistency (e.g., Cronbach's α , McDonald's ω) could be computed retrospectively. The questionnaire findings should accordingly be interpreted as descriptive indicators of perceived group functioning, not as psychometrically validated measures of latent constructs.
- (3) Absence of inferential statistical testing. Because only aggregated group-level scores and proportions have been preserved, inferential statistical testing (non-parametric tests, effect-size estimators, confidence intervals) could not be conducted. The quantitative component of the study is therefore strictly descriptive and exploratory, and the comparisons reported between the two configurations should be interpreted as patterns of association observed in the available data, rather than as statistically tested differences.
- (4) Sociometric analysis and ethical residual. The sociometric component is restricted to descriptive structural indicators (reciprocity, isolation, rejection patterns, tie distribution); formal Social Network Analysis metrics—such as density, clustering coefficient, or degree and betweenness centrality—were not computed because the original individual-level binary nomination matrices were not preserved, and formal sociogram-based visualizations could not be produced for the same reason. Although a comprehensive set of ethical safeguards was adopted (Section 3.6), no formal post-administration debriefing session was conducted; this minor residual should be addressed in future replications.
- (5) Qualitative component. The qualitative analysis was conducted within an exploratory and complementary role in the broader mixed-methods design. Two coders independently coded the corpus and resolved discrepancies through discussion, but no formal inter-rater agreement coefficient (e.g., Cohen's κ) was computed, and no structured codebook with operational definitions was produced. The interpretive distinction between operational and deliberative participation is offered as a tentative typology derived from the qualitative material, rather than as an empirically measured construct; no observational or discourse-analytic data were collected to substantiate claims regarding the cognitive complexity of peer interaction.

Despite these limitations, the study offers two methodological strengths: the use of the same teacher across both pedagogical configurations, which substantially reduces between-teacher variability; and the integration of structural, perceptual, and qualitative levels of evidence, which makes visible patterns of association that would have remained invisible if any single level of evidence had been analyzed in isolation.

Future research could overcome these limitations through stronger comparative designs incorporating random assignment, pretest measures of academic achievement, group cohesion and sociometric structure, larger and multi-school samples, longitudinal follow-up, preservation of individual-level data to support inferential analyses and the application of formal SNA metrics, observational and discourse-analytic data to substantiate claims regarding the cognitive complexity of peer interaction, as well as to integrate additional variables—such as cognitive load—that may help explain the relationship between methodological openness and the social dimension of learning. Future replications should also preserve a formal post-administration debriefing protocol when negative-nomination items are administered to adolescent participants. Such research would substantially strengthen

the comparative claims that can be drawn regarding the relationship between methodological openness and the social sustainability of learning.

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